

Memorial Stones of Sindh, Pakistan: Typology and Iconography

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Abstract

The subject of memorial stones is a new addition to the archaeology and religion studies in Pakistan in general and Sindh in particular. We know that there is a growing interest on this subject in India. Therefore, this paper deals with the memorial stones of Tharparkar district of Sindh, Pakistan. Memorial stones are found in almost every historic village in Tharparkar district which are worshipped by Hindu community of Tharparkar. There are many local terms which are used for the memorial stones. The paper has been divided into two parts, the first part focuses on the typological and the second iconographical aspects of the memorials stones.

Key Words- Memorial stones, Hero-stones, Sati-stones, typology, iconography

The practice of erecting memorial stones to commemorate the heroic death of a warrior was widespread in the early medieval period in Sindh. One cannot say with certainty when was the first memorial stone or pillar was erected. Based on dated memorial stones one can safely say that the memorial stones were in vogue in the 10th and 11th centuries. Memorial towers, pillars and stones are found in different parts of Sindh. Memorial stones are erected for men who died as heroes in battle or met with an unnatural death. In close connection with them figure the innumerable sati monuments.

The present paper deals with the memorial stones of Tharparkar District focusing on typology and iconography. Administratively Tharparkar District is divided into six Talukas- Diplo, Mithi, Chachro, Dhahali, Islamakot and Nagarparkar. They are found in all Talukas of the District. They were erected in memory of the heroes (*Vir, jhujhar*) who took part in a battle, fight, skirmish or scuffle and died fighting the enemy. Memorial stones are considered as anthropological data for a society or community to know about socio-economic, socio-religious, and socio-political events (Takuria et al 2011: 175). Memorial stones, known as *pariya* in Parkari and *loharti* in Dahatki languages have been found in larger numbers in Mithi and Nagarparkar Talukas of Tharparkar District.

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Types of Memorial Stones

Memorial stones are known by various names in Tharparkar District, Sindh. Traditionally they are divided into eight types: *Pariyo*, *Gauchar Pariyo*, *Vir Jo Jod Pariyo*, *Vanjara Pariyo*, *Loharti*, *Khambhi*, *Jaryo*, *Nishidi*, *Dagalo*, *Thesa*, *Chuca*.

1. *Pariyo*

There is no consensus of opinion on the exact derivation of the word *pariyo*. According to one school of thought, the word originated from the Sanskrit noun *pala* meaning protector or guardian, its context here being: he who died to uphold or protect his code of ethics. Thus *pariyo* is the vernacular equivalent of the classical *pala*. Initially, the *pariyas* or *paliyas* must have signified the commemorative stones of those who died for a cause. In the course of time, this specific definition faded into a more general one, implying any type of memorial stone (Doshi 1982: 165). Another school of thought claims that the word *pariyo* or *paliya* comes from the root *pal*, meaning to protect or guard. The subscribers to this view argue that, since it is we who look after the stone-tablets of our forebears and offer them worship, we are the protectors of the memorial stones, hence *pariya* or *paliya* indicates those that are protected (Doshi: 165). The term *pariyo* is only used for hero-stones in Nagarparkar Taluka (Fig.1).

2. *Gauchar Pariyo*

The term *gauchar* is used to refer to communal pasture. Memorial stones containing the image of a cow were installed on the communal pastures which indicated boundary markers between the two villages.

3. *Vir Jo Jod pariyo*

Land was granted to brave persons in the past. Other types of grants namely gardens, villages and wells were also granted to perpetuate the memory of the deceased heroes. The granted land, locally called *jod*, was not cultivated. Only cattle were allowed to graze in *Vir- Jo- Jod*. Memorial stones are also found at *Vir-Jo-Jod*. This type of *pariya* contains the image of a cow. There are several *Vir Jo Jod Pariya* in Nagarparkar. One of such memorial stones is found at Dongri village.

4. *Vanjara Pariya*

These stones are found at the tanks of Vanjara tribe. The *Vanjara pariya* resemble *govardhana* pillar with four sculpted sides indicating that the tanks were either built or commissioned by them. On one

side of the *pariya* is always depicted the image of a cow with a suckling calf. Three other sides depict *yoni* and *linga*, the sun and moon. One of such Vanjara *pariya* is found at Ranasar at Lakarkhadiyo village (Fig.2).

5. Loharti

This term is equivalent of *pariyo* and *khambhi* which is used for all engraved memorial stone tablets in Mithi, Chachro and Diplo Talukas (Fig.3). There is no convincing definition of the word *loharti*. According to local people, the *loharti* was erected for both *jhujhar* and *sati*. Moreover, it may derive from the Sanskrit word *lohar* (iron-smith). In the medieval period, the iron-smiths, not *salawats* (stone-engravers) were commissioned to make a *loharti*. Therefore, it is more related to their skill and tool (hammer) which they used to make *loharti*. The possible explanation for this term is that it is a stone tablet chiselled/engraved with a hammer.

6. Khambhi

Another word that is used for memorials is *khambhi*. This term is only used in Nagarparkar Taluka. *Khambhi* is erected for those who take their lives or commit self-immolation. These memorials are called *khambhis* and not *pariyas* even though they look alike. *Pariyas* are erected only for those heroes who died in battle or defending their villages or cattle, whereas *khambhis* are erected for those who committed self-immolation or who became *satis*. Put differently, *khambhis* are erected for only *satis* while *pariyas* for heroes (*vira*, *jhujhars*). One only hears *sati ji khambhi* not *pariyo* of *sati* in Nagarparkar (Fig.4).

It is believed that the word *khambhi* has come from the Sanskrit word *stambha* meaning a column (Doshi 1982:170). Maddock argues that the word *khambhi* is generally accepted as deriving from the Sanskrit *stambha* and its derivative *khambha*. *Khambhas* are a type of menhir that date from Vedic times or even earlier (Maddock 1993:107).

7. Jarya

This term is in vogue in Nagarparkar Taluka. The term is used in the local Parkari language for “accidentally discovered architectural member of a Jain temple or shrine”. This accidentally discovered fragment of Jain temple or shrine was installed and worshipped by the local community. Such memorial stones (*jaryas*) are found near Mokrio (Fig.5) and at Umedo Jo Wandio (Fig.6) villages in Nagarparkar.

8. Nishidi

Nishidi stones are only found in Nagarprakar Taluka. The term is derived from the Sanskrit root word *sad* (*sid*). There are other derivative forms like *nisadiya* and also with the *ka* suffix, *nisadyaka*, *nisidika*, meaning a seat, a sitting place, a seat specially taken for any religious rite, a place of rest when one resorts to *sallekhana* or *Samadhi-marna*. *Nisidhi* memorials are spots where pious monks, nuns, householders and housewives took their seats while submitting to voluntary death or where they got their final rest. Thus *nishidhi* is a post-mortem memorial, possibly marking the spot where the pious individual breathed his last according to religious rites, or where his body was burnt or where his bone relics were buried (Upadhye 1982:46).

The rite of *sallekhana* warrants detachment from worldly and emotional bonds, realization and confession of mistakes, subjugation of the senses and renunciation of all that aides physical existence. Renunciation of worldly possessions, mediation under the guidance of a teacher and adoption of guarded fasting, are some of the essential pre-conditions of this process (Settar and Korisettar 1982:284).

Nishidi stones are found in many villages of Nagarparkar (Fig.7).

9. Dagalo

The term *dagalo* is used to refer to a small heap of stones raised in commemoration of an individual. Doshi (1982:171) believes that it is a cairn consisting of a heap of loose stones. It is customary for the relatives of the deceased to throw a small stone on the heap whenever they pass by. The terms *cago*, *caglio*, *Chaga saga* (heap) are used in Kutch, Gujarat and Saurashtra for a small heap of stones. *Saga* seems to be derived from Sanskrit *sringa* "top" (Shelat 2006: 189). The *dagalo* memorials are found in different villages of Nagarparkar. The famous *dagalo* memorials are those of Khetoji at Berano and Hamirji at Asalri (Fig.8).

10. Thesa

It is a roughly hewn block of stone which is raised along with *pariyo*. People who could not afford to raise *pariyo* would set up *thesa*. *Thesa* memorials are found in all six Talukas of Tharparkar District but they are numerous in Nagarparkar (Fig 9).

11. Chucho/Chucha

The term is used to refer to the materiality of stone. It is a type of metamorphic and igneous rock that

is locally available. It has small holes resembling small-eyed person. Based on this analogy, these stones are called *chucho* or *chuchas*. People removed these *chucha* from deposits where they are found and dressed them before installing as a memorial to the dead. Some stones were carved while most of them were undecorated and installed without any dressing. *Chucha* memorials are the earliest memorial stones which are found in different parts of Tharparkar (Fig.10). They were raised much before the coming of the Sodha Rajputs to Thar in the 12th century. Most of these belong to the Parmar Rajputs and their soldiers who once held sway over the Thar Desert.

Iconography

A memorial stone is either cylindrical, square or rectangular upright standing stone. It always faces east. The memorial stone has two basic parts-the carvings and inscription below.

There are many detailed differences in the iconographic appearance in both hero and *sati*-stones which I discuss below.

1.Pariyo/Loharti with a horse rider: This iconographic feature is most commonly seen on *pariyas/lohartis* of all Talukas of Tharparkar District. In this the hero is shown in warrior attire riding a horse holding a spear in his right hand and bow in the left. In some cases, a shield is depicted behind a figure of the deceased hero. On some hero-stones are depicted two horse riders. In this case, it shows that the deceased was either from the same family or relatives.

2. Pariyo with a horse rider holding a gun: There are some hero-stones which show hero holding a gun. There are two examples in which heroes are shown holding guns. One belongs to Arjun Koli at Old Qasibo and the other to Ratan Singh at Nagarparkar town.

3.Pariyo with a camel rider: On some hero-stones instead of horse, a hero is shown riding a camel. Such hero-stones belong to a Rabari. Rabari community is found in Nagarparkar Taluka. Such stones with a depiction of camel riders are only found in Nagarparkar.

4.Pariyo with a standing figure: A deceased hero is shown holding a sword in one hand and shield in other in a protective manner.

5.Pariyo with a depiction of cow: There are several *pariyas* which depict a figure of a cow. On some *pariyas* cow is shown with its calf. These *pariyas* are mostly located at the tanks of Vanjara tribe, on *gauchar* land and outside any village.

6.Pariyas with a man piercing dagger in his neck: This motif is seen on some *pariyas* in Nagarparkar in

which man is shown piercing a dagger in his neck (Fig.11). This is called a *traga* or *kattari* which was practiced by Charans. This was also common among Bhats and Brahmans. In popular belief Charans are believed to be living deities and their men call themselves *deviputras*. Their curse was dreaded because of their capacity to perform *traga*, that is, killing themselves in the presence of their opponent with a dagger or sword and sprinkling blood over the enemy, cursing him with total destruction (Shelat 2006:189). Weinberger-Thomas (2000:65) believes that there are more than 32 forms of *traga*. *Traga* by fire, known as *телио* (from *tel* oil) constitutes the supreme form of voluntary death for the Charans. Joma Charani also performed *traga* by fire to protest against the Rind Baloch at Mithrio Charan in Chachro Taluka during the British period. This was *телио* form of *traga* which she performed .

7.*Nishidi* with *kirtimukha* and other symbols: All the memorials of Jaina are depicted with *kirtimukha*, a lotus and an ascetic with suspending earrings. Male figure is also shown with anklets and bracelets (Fig.12).

8.*Khambhi/Loharati* (sati-stone) with a dead husband on her lap: The *sati* figure is shown holding her husband in her lap. Her right hand is raised in *abaya-mudra* posture. The uppermost section of the *sati*-stone is invariably depicted with the sun and moon. On some *sati*-stones a pair of peacocks has also been noticed. Those *sati*-stones located in Mithi, Chachro and Diplo Talukas are devoid of the representations of the sun and the moon on the upper section of the memorial stones.

9.*Khambhi* with a standing figure of *sati*: *Sati* is shown standing holding a water pot in her left hand a rosary in the other. Sometimes she is shown in *namaskara* pose. In some cases, the *sati* is depicted with both her hands placed on the chest.

10.*Khambhi* with a raised hand: Instead of a standing figure of *sati*, her raised arm bent at the elbow is depicted on some of the *sati*-stones. This iconographic feature is only found on *sati*-stones in Nagarparkar Taluka.

11.*Khambhi* with a horse rider and a raised arm: On some *sati*-stones both horse rider and a raised arm of *sati* is depicted in front or behind the figure of the horse rider.

12.*Khambhi* with a standing figure of *sati* and a raised arm: A *sati* is shown standing holding a water-pot in her right hand. In front of the figure depicts a raised arm of *sati*. This is the popular iconography of *sati* which can be seen in several *khambhis* (*sati*-stones) in Nagarparkar Taluka.

13.*Khambhi* with a horse rider and a standing figure of *sati*: Some *sati*-stones depict the figures of both a hero riding on a horse with *sati* standing in front or behind him.

14.*Jarya* with figures of deities and ascetics: The figures of Jaina ascetics and guardian deities are depicted on these memorial stones. Some Hindu deities are also shown on these *jaryas* (memorial stones). One such *jarya* depicting a Hindu deity is located at Viravah.

15.*Samadhi* with geometric designs: Some *samadhi*-stone of Nath Jogis are depicted with geometric designs. These *samadhi* were erected in memory of those who took living *samadhi*. This practice was common among both Nath Jogis and Jaina ascetics (Fig.13).

Conclusion

The majority of the memorial stones was erected in memory of the heroes who laid their lives while fighting cattle-lifters. In other districts of Sindh are memorial towers (Fig.14) which were erected in memory of the cattle retrievers. They are found in the hilly regions of Karachi, Thatta, Jamshoro and Dadu Districts where the main mode of subsistence is cattle. Commemorative/memorial towers erected in memory of the heroes are called *Mahi* and *Churio*. The term *Mahi* (earth, beloved) is in vogue in Karachi and Jamshoro Districts whereas *Churio* is used in the Khirthar Range in Dadu District. One such memorial tower is also found in Nagarparkar Taluka which is locally called 'Pollan astan'. It was erected in memory of a Rathore ruler of Nayer in Jodhpur. He chased cattle-lifters who stole cattle from his village. He engaged them in a fight near Gori temple where he died fighting them. Later, his descendants erected a commemorative tower in his memory which still stands though in very bad state of preservation.

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Fig.1 Paliyas at Berarai, Nagarparkar

Fig.2 Vanjara Pariyo at Lakarkhadiyo village, Nagarparkar

Fig.3 Lohartis at Malhanhor Veena village, Mithi

Fig.4. A khmabi (sati-stone) at Old Qasibo village, Nagarparkar

Fig. 5. A Jaryo at Mokrio village, Nagarparkar

Fig. 6. A Jaryo at Umed Jo Wandio village, Nagarparkar

Fig. 7. Nishidi stone at old Mokrio village, Nagarparkar

Fig. 8. Daglo memorial of Hamirji at Asalri village, Nagarparkar

Fig.9. Khambi and Thesa memorials at old Qasibo village, Nagarparkar

Fig. 10. Chucho memorial at Veesar village, Mithi

Fig. 11. Memorial stone showing a Charan piercing (Kattari) dagger in his neck, Mokrio Village, Nagarparkar

Fig.12. Nishidi stone depicting kirtimukha, Old Mokrio village, Nagarparkar

Fig.13. Samadhi stone at Old Adhigam, Nagarparkar